

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:

Impacts on Climate and the Earth system

Infrastructure design v.1.0

Deliverable D7.4

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<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

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Table of contents

1. Publishable summary	4
2. Work performed and main achievements	5
2.1 Description of the work performed	5
2.1.1 Data Layer (OCEAN ICE-DI-DL).....	6
2.1.2 O:I-DI and METADATA management	9
2.1.3 Service Layer (OCEAN ICE-DI-SL)	10
2.1.3 Application Layer (OCEAN ICE-DI-AL).....	11
2.2 References	15
2.3 Open Science	15
3. Results	16
3.1.1 Metadata	16
3.1.1 Data Services	17
4. Impact.....	18
Appendix A: OCEAN:ICE-ID Metadata Schema	19

1. Publishable summary

The goal of OCEAN ICE is to evaluate the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet (AIS) and Southern Ocean processes on sea level rise, deep water formation, and ocean circulation to enhance predictions of how changes in the Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets impact global climate. To achieve this, historical datasets, observations from the period spanning 2022 to 2024, and numerical models, including the development of coupled ice sheet-ocean and ice sheet-ocean-climate models, will be employed.

The WP7 Data Management team has taken over the legacy of the EU Horizon 2020 SO-CHIC project to contribute to making Southern Ocean data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable in the long term. As described in the OCEAN ICE [Data Management Plan](#) (Novellino & Misurale, 2023; Novellino & Dapuzo, 2024), WP7 focuses on in situ data.

OCEAN ICE moves beyond open access in implementing open science practices while adhering to the principles FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) principles: OCEAN ICE infrastructure is designed to provide immediate, free access and interoperability for collected data. It adopts open data management software tools (e.g., ERDDAP™, GeoServer, GeoNetwork) and ensures that OCEAN ICE data is immediately integrable and accessible via the European Commission public data repositories.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

The overall goal of the OCEAN ICE WP7 is to design, develop and operate data management solutions that adhere to FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016; Tanhua et al., 2019), ensure the adoption of best practices, promote interoperability, and facilitate data sharing.

OCEAN ICE builds upon and evolves the data management architecture that supports ¹[[SOOSmap](https://soosmap.aq/)], an interactive web portal for oceanographic data visualization and dissemination (Bordoni et al., 2024). SOOSmap was developed and is hosted by the European Marine Observations and Data Network (EMODnet) Physics for the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) and is supported by the EU H2020 Southern Ocean Carbon and Heat Impact on Climate ²[[SOCHIC](https://www.sochic-h2020.eu/)] project (Bricher et al., 2018, Gorringer et al., 2021). SOOSmap serves curated and standardized observation data from oceanographic and Antarctic research programs across many nations and scientific disciplines. It is built around individual observing platforms or sampling events (e.g., an Argo float or plankton trawl). Specifically, it allows users to discover and access circumpolar data from various international research centers, data assemblers, oceanographic repositories, and marine infrastructures in the Antarctic.

OCEAN ICE data infrastructure (OCEAN ICE -DI) is based on open software tools that ensure FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and machine-to-machine interoperability (e.g., ERDDAP, GeoNetwork, GeoServer), utilizing European harmonized and controlled vocabularies (e.g., SeaDataNet EDMO vocabulary) as a standard thesaurus for data publishing tools. O:I-DI also integrates a data portal (Deliverable D7.11 – Novellino & Paolini, 2024) and an educational page to demonstrate how to use O:I data to develop ocean products.

As planned, the OCEAN ICE -DI is based on three logical layers:

- 1) data ingestion/connection,
- 2) data service layer and
- 3) data presentation/dissemination.

¹ <https://soosmap.aq/>

² <https://www.sochic-h2020.eu/>

Figure 1. OCEAN ICE-DI logical architecture

The current OCEAN ICE -DI is operated by two virtual machines: VMs, 2.10GHz processing power, 4 cores, 32GB RAM, running on CentOS with 500GB disk each). These VMs efficiently operate Docker containers, which, while resembling VMs, exhibit more relaxed isolation properties for sharing the underlying Operating System (OS) among applications.

2.1.1 Data Layer (OCEAN ICE-DI-DL)

The OCEAN ICE -DI-DL supports the ingestion of freshly recorded in situ data and the integration of already existing relevant in situ data (and products). Regarding newly collected data, OCEAN ICE –DI-DL is designed to manage both operational near real-time data and delayed mode data.

Operational near real-time data refers to the systematic, long-term routine measurement, and dissemination of ocean (and atmospheric) data as soon as it is collected. The Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)³ as identified 13 operational observing networks (e.g., ARGO, buoys, ship-based hydrographic investigations, Ship of Opportunity, etc.) that provide long-term, global, high-quality, in situ ocean observations. These networks use various technologies to track changes in global ocean conditions and variables such as temperature, currents, waves, sea level, salinity, carbon, and oxygen, which are vital for characterizing changes in the global ocean environment. The collected data are transmitted to global or thematic data centers, where they undergo quality control and standardization. This data informs weather and climate forecasts, environmental assessments, marine ecosystem monitoring, and coastal region management, directly contributing to skillful forecasts and product development.

Typically, data collections supporting GOOS are made publicly and freely available to anyone wishing to use them. For example, ARGO profiles are available within 12-24 hours as near real-time data sets, following an automated quality control procedure. The data are ingested into the Global Telecommunications System (GTS) and used for operational ocean and atmospheric forecasting. Argo data profiles are further quality

³ <https://goosocean.org/who-we-are/observations-coordination-group/global-ocean-observing-networks/>

controlled as delayed mode profiles, typically within one year of receiving the data from the Core Argo float, with periodic reviews thereafter. All data, both raw and quality controlled, are made available to users through two Global Data Acquisition Centres (GDACs), Coriolis (France) and NOAA (US), and associated repositories, services, and downstream platforms (e.g., Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet, etc.).

A crucial element in this process is the registration of the deployment plan (and assignment of the unique WIGOS-WMO code) within the OCEANOPS system. OCEANOPS assists new deployment teams in ensuring that platforms are accurately recorded, and that metadata are transmitted. Providing the ID assigned by OCEANOPS to WP7 is essential for linking operational data (funded by OCEAN ICE into the OCEAN ICE -DI.. is essential for linking operational data (funded by OCEAN ICE) into the OCEAN ICE -DI.

OCEAN ICE has already deployed several ARGO floats. As soon as these begin delivering data to GDAC, the newly recorded OCEAN ICE data is synchronized with the OCEAN ICE-DI, where the OCEAN ICE -DI-DL enriches data with more detailed metadata, and makes data publicly available for downstream use.

O:I ARGO dataset:
https://erddap.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/tabledap/ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE.html

The figure shows a screenshot of the OCEAN:ICE ERDDAP portal. On the left, there is a table with the following columns: PLATFORMCODE, WMO, project_name, and pi_name. The table lists 14 ARGO float deployments. On the right, there is a map interface with a text overlay that reads: "We need to 'normalize' data and add/tag 'O:I' for stakeholders integration".

PLATFORMCODE	WMO	project_name	pi_name
1902687	1902687	Argo UK	Pierre Dutrieux
3902582	3902582	Argo UK	Pierre Dutrieux
4903780	4903780	Argo AWI	Markus JANOUT
4903780	4903780	Argo AWI	Markus Janout
4903786	4903786	Argo UK	Pierre Dutrieux
5907087	5907087	ARGO AWI	Markus JANOUT
5907087	5907087	ARGO AWI	Markus Janout
5907093	5907093	Argo UK	Pierre Dutrieux
6990621	6990621	ARGO AWI	Markus JANOUT
6990621	6990621	ARGO AWI	Markus Janout
6990622	6990622	Argo AWI	Markus JANOUT
6990622	6990622	Argo AWI	Markus Janout

Figure 2. OCEAN ICE ARGO deployments in OCEAN ICE-DI and O:I stakeholder portal (EMODnet)

Delayed mode refers to the measurement and dissemination of ocean (and atmospheric) data after the collected data have undergone meticulous and specific analysis to identify and mark issues such as spikes, offsets, and drifts. Typically, delayed mode data are available 1-2 years after the measurements are taken or the platform is recovered. Researchers often publish scientific reports (papers) that accompany and complement the delayed mode or validated datasets. These datasets are usually deposited into community databases or a National Oceanographic Data Center database. While these different databases are generally FAIR-compliant, datasets may be organized in various ways, both inter- and intra-databases, resulting in a semi-optimal solution for data use.

As an example, glider data from the PANGAEA, which is a OCEAN ICE -DI trusted federated node, trusted federated node, may be made available in different formats, such as ⁴[[OBJ](#)], as ⁵[[OBJ](#)], or as ⁶[[OBJ](#)]. If a user wants to utilize all three examples, they must download the collections and then convert them into a common format while managing metadata and dictionaries.

To enhance the available services and facilitate data (re)usability, as anticipated, OCEAN ICE -DI has designed a dedicated workflow for managing and harmonizing delayed mode data. This workflow builds on the current process: once the researcher or principal investigator (PI) has quality-checked, flagged the data, deposited the processed dataset into a trusted repository, and received a unique ID (DOI) for that dataset, the PI must either drop a copy of the validated collection into the O:I-DI-DL delayed mode delivery buffer or provide WP7 with the dataset federation specification APIs.

Access to the drop area is managed through selective endpoint authorization, allowing access only from specified IP addresses or hosts with fully qualified domain names (FQDNs) and rejecting connections and access attempts from devices outside the authorized list.

The notification to WP7 triggers the OCEAN ICE -DI Figure 3⁷), which verifies and normalizes the data and metadata format (applying the minimum set of common metadata with dictionaries recommended by the OCEAN ICE DMP (e.g. the BODC NVS P0x for parameters, ISO for time and datum etc), publishes the normalized version of the data collection for internal approval and validation, and, once approved, pushes the collection into the OCEAN ICE -DI-SL. The new data is then made available according to FAIR principles and offered through services that allow users to specify how they wish to consume the data (in terms of data format, subsets, APIs, etc.)

Figure 3. delayed mode data management procedure workflow

⁴ <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.967727>

⁵ <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.904659>

⁶ <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.877390>

As anticipated, delayed mode data and other existing data are (have to be) available in O:I federated trusted repositories, which are community databases and the National Oceanographic Data Center database. More specifically, currently, OCEAN ICE is ⁷[7](https://www.pangaea.de/), UK P ⁸[8](https://www.bas.ac.uk/team/business-teams/information-services/uk-polar-data-centre/), ⁹[9](https://www.bodc.ac.uk/data/bodc_database/nodb/), ¹⁰[10](https://www.seanoe.org/), ¹¹[11](https://tds0.ifremer.fr/thredds/CORIOLIS.html), ¹²[12](https://snd.se/en/catalogue/search/Oden), ¹³[13](https://npdc.nl/dataset), ¹⁴[14](https://data.npolar.no/dataset). Other data are integrated via SOOS federated nodes.

Figure 4. Detail of the Data layer in the OCEAN ICE-DI

2.1.2 O:I-DI and METADATA management

As described the OCEAN ICE-DI-DL operates a metadata harmonization and normalization process, which is crucial for having fully described and consumable resources. Metadata contextualizes other data by providing information such as when and how it was generated, making the data easier to find, understand, use, and manage. The metadata is stored according to the specifications established by the file format specified in the manual and must include information necessary to use the data properly and to facilitate machine-to-machine communication. Metadata contains the Digital Object Identifier (DOI), a unique number or code used to identify the dataset to which the data belongs. Typically, DOIs are intended to be unique within a global context. Metadata may also include a product identifier (ID), an alphanumeric code used to identify the specific product containing a set of datasets.

Metadata is accompanied by dictionaries and vocabularies that consist of technical definitions required to fully understand the data standard's information. Appendix A: OCEAN:ICE-ID Metadata Schema describes the recommended and adopted metadata model for O:I-DI.

⁷ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

⁸ <https://www.bas.ac.uk/team/business-teams/information-services/uk-polar-data-centre/>

⁹ https://www.bodc.ac.uk/data/bodc_database/nodb/

¹⁰ <https://www.seanoe.org/>

¹¹ <https://tds0.ifremer.fr/thredds/CORIOLIS.html>

¹² <https://snd.se/en/catalogue/search/Oden>

¹³ <https://npdc.nl/dataset>

¹⁴ <https://data.npolar.no/dataset>

2.1.3 Service Layer (OCEAN ICE-DI-SL)

To facilitate data harmonization and function as an integrator and translator to enhance data use and interoperability, it is important to use common open tools for querying and viewing data collections and products. In line with the GOOS Observation Coordination Group (OCG) recommendations, O:I-DI-SL is operated by the OCEAN ICE -DI-SL-ERDDAP™ and the OCEAN ICE -DI-SL-GeoNetwork.

ERDDAP™ data server is open-source software written in Java that builds upon the open-source ideals of the OPeNDAP, WCS, SOS and OBIS standards. ERDDAP™ data server supports several common data file formats (html table, netcdf, csv, txt, mat, json, etc.) and output files are created on-the-fly in any of this format. It implements FGDC Web Accessible Folder (WAF) with FGDC-STD-001-1998 and ISO 19115 WAF with ISO 19115-2/19139.

O:I-DI-SL-ERDDAP → <https://erddap.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/index.html>

Figure 5. OCEAN ICE-DI-SL-ERDDAP

Another tool that is increasing in popularity and use is GeoNetwork. GeoNetwork, based on an open source (GNOS) project, is a free and open source (FOSS) cataloguing application for spatially referenced resources. GeoNetwork provides a web interface to search geospatial data across multiple catalogues. The search provides full-text search as well as faceted search on keywords, resource types, organisations, scale, etc. The catalogue is able to describe geospatial layers, services, maps and also non geographic datasets. GeoNetwork implements WxS, OGC, ISO 19115/119/110 standards used for spatial resources and also the Dublin Core format usually used for open data portals.

OCEAN ICE -DI-SL-GEONETWORK → <https://catalog.s4oceanice.eu/geonetwork/srv/ita/catalog.search#/home>

These two tools enhance data discoverability, accessibility, and interoperability, serving both the service level (by providing APIs and machine-to-machine services for internal use) and the application level (by offering cataloging functionality and machine-to-machine tools for external users).

To maximize the benefits of these technologies, data should be “open by default” and licensed under an open license, preferably CC-BY (credit to the author) or CC0 (public domain).

This approach also supports OCEAN ICE stakeholders, such as EMODnet (Physics) and SOOSmap, by enabling them to link and discover OCEAN ICE data in accordance with FAIR and open interoperability principles.

2.1.3 Application Layer (OCEAN ICE-DI-AL)

OCEAN ICE-DI-AL is designed to provide the Southern Ocean community with information on sea surface temperature, salinity, currents, sea ice extent, and biological productivity, among other parameters.

As anticipated OCEAN ICE is inheriting the legacy of the EU H2020 SO-CHIC project by maintaining and updating SOOSmap. The Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) bridges oceanographic and polar science programs, forming one of the most internationally integrated scientific communities, largely due to the logistical challenges of conducting research in these remote waters. The users of Southern Ocean data are highly diverse, with varying needs and expertise. Serving such a heterogeneous research community requires data management systems that are flexible and focused on integrating existing data products, rather than duplicating efforts.

SOOS is collaborating with both the scientific and data communities to design an ecosystem of data management tools, catalogs, and systems tailored for polar oceanographic research. What sets this system apart from other data aggregators is that SOOSmap serves a uniquely diverse community, drawing data from numerous nations and scientific disciplines, all while focusing on a single geographic region.

By supporting SOOSmap, OCEAN ICE has a fast track to make its data more visible to the SOOS (and international) community (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6. O:I data in SOOSmap

By integrating data from multiple sources into a single platform, SOOSmap enables researchers to make informed decisions and advance our understanding of the Southern Ocean's role in global climate and ocean circulation and makes OCEAN ICE contribution widely known and acknowledged (Figure 7).

Figure 7. SOOSmap credits

OCEAN ICE -DI-AL is also developing two further tools: the O:I data portal, which will offer new ways to search for southern ocean data (see Deliverable 7.9 for a preliminary portal design), and a pivotal integration of Jupyter Book, an open-source tool that plays a crucial role in collaborative online book design using Jupyter Notebooks, which enhances the project's accessibility and fosters effective collaboration among developers.

OCEAN ICE DI-AL-JB → <https://literacy.s4oceanice.eu/intro.html>

Each chapter is complemented with a colab script that uses OCEAN ICE data and can be executed to see outcomes from the analysis of OCEAN ICE data.

OCEAN:ICE
Erddap
Analysis of Antarctic Sea Ice
Extension: Annual Maxima and Minima
Analysis of Antarctic Sea Level: Monthly Mean

```
'''This block of code gets a list of geojsons containing informations about the antarctic ice
The function reduceFun creates a dictionary with the data needed for the following cells of
from functools import reduce
import requests
import json

resp = requests.get('https://prod-geoserver.emodnet-physics.eu/geoserver/EMODnet/ows?service

iceJson = resp.content
iceData = json.loads(iceJson)

def reduceFun(a, c):
    if c['properties']['year'] not in a.keys():
        a[c['properties']['year']] = {'type': "FeatureCollection", 'features': []}
        a[c['properties']['year']]['features'].append(c)
    return a

iceDict = reduce(reduceFun, iceData['features'], {})
```

▶ Show code cell source

▶ Show code cell source

Figure 8. Example of a chapter in the O:I-DI-AL-JB

2.2 References

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2.3 Open Science

OCEAN ICEDI is designed to support and foster Open Science practices. As described in the previous sections it adopts and develops open tools, support best practices, support open science (with a focus on SOOS community), develops new tools (e.g. the OCEAN ICEDI-AL-JB) to facilitate data processing understanding and crowdsourcing in developing/updating new processing methods.

Each publication, deliverable, milestone, presentation and dataset uploaded to Zenodo or SEANOE, that are both OPENAire compliant repositories, is given a unique DOI (Digital Object Identifier) which identifies the content and provides a persistent link to its location on the Internet. To enhance the visibility, discoverability, and accessibility of research outputs within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and beyond, it is essential to ensure that document published on ZENODO and SEANOE are interoperable with OPENAire. To ensure smooth interoperability, the following aspects are important: choose Open Licenses (CC-BY), include Funding Project Information, use Metadata compliant with standards and current vocabularies, provide Persistent Identifiers (DOIs, ORCIDs), link Related Resources. WP7 is developing a Guide about all these aspects.

About the datasets production monitoring, below an example. Since the type of PID declared is a DOI, the PID reported is a link starting with DOI (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12166097>). In the section URL of the repository, indicate the link to the repository when the dataset is published. In the example, it is <https://zenodo.org/records/12166097>

3. Results

3.1.1 Metadata

OCEAN ICE supports high quality metadata and adoption of controlled vocabularies. To this end it was important to register the project (and its partners) under key European directories, namely, the 15^[OBJ] that hosts the ocean data projects list, and the European Directory of Marine Organisations 16^[OBJ] that hosts the data provider/owner inventory.

OCEAN ICE -EDMERP → <https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/report/13721>

OCEAN ICE -EDMO codes → Table 1^[OBJ]

Table 1. OCEAN ICEpartners' EDMO

Consortium Members	Consortium Short Name	EDMO
Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut	DMI	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/469
NORCE Norwegian Research Centre	NORCE	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5153
Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum Fur Polar-Und Meeresforschung	AWI	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1368
Centre National De La Recherche Scientifique	CNRS	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/2895
Universiteit Utrecht	UU	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1429
ETT SPA	ETT	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/2764
Université Libre de Bruxelles	ULB	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/717
Ecole Normale Supérieure	ENS-LMD	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/4763
Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research	PIK	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/3445
University of Gothenburg	UGOT	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/3984
NORSK POLARINSTITUTT	NPI	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1349
European Polar Board	EPB	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5859
United Kingdom Research and Innovation	UKRI-BAS	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/41 https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/4946
University of Northumbria at Newcastle	UNN	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/5400
University of Southampton	UoS	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/1801
University of Reading	UREAD	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/2080
The University of Liverpool	ULIVERPOOL	https://edmo.seadatanet.org/report/3488
National Antarctic Scientific Center	NASC	in process

¹⁵ <https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/>

¹⁶ <https://edmo.seadatanet.org/>

3.1.1 Data Services

OCEAN ICE -DI-SL-ERDDAP → <https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/index.html>

OCEAN ICE -DI-SL-GNW → <https://catalog.s4oceanice.eu/geonetwork/> OCEAN ICE I-DI-AL-JB
→ <https://literacy.s4oceanice.eu/intro.html>

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

OCEAN:ICE WP7 is actively achieving Objective 7 (O7) by establishing a robust data infrastructure that ensures free and open access to all data generated. This infrastructure is designed to support FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles and is fully compliant with INSPIRE regulations. By closely integrating with SOOS, EMODnet, and Copernicus data delivery services, the project facilitates seamless data consolidation and delivery. Additionally, OCEAN

is collaborating with key stakeholders—including SOOS (Southern Ocean Observing System), SAMOC (South Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation), EPB (European Polar Board), the EU Polar Cluster, and EU-PolarNet 2—to ensure that data practices align with international standards and contribute meaningfully to global climate assessments and policymaking. Through direct partnerships and the involvement of investigators in international science coordination, climate assessment, and policy bodies, the project is setting and adapting metadata standards and proposing best practices that enhance the reach and impact of its data across these diverse communities.

Appendix A: OCEAN:ICE-ID Metadata Schema

Variable name	Description	Data type	Description	Mandatory	Vocabulary
Dataset	accessible				
Dataset	dataset_ID				
NC_GLOBAL	_NCProperties				
NC_GLOBAL	acknowledgement				
NC_GLOBAL	author				
NC_GLOBAL	author_email				
NC_GLOBAL	Callsign				
NC_GLOBAL	cdm_data_type	string	Data type according to Common Data Model (e.g., TrajectoryProfile, TimeSeries, Grid, Point, Other)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	cdm_altitude_proxy				
NC_GLOBAL	cdm_timeseries_variables	string			
NC_GLOBAL	circular_redundancy_code				
NC_GLOBAL	citation	string			
NC_GLOBAL	conventions	string	Conventions	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	contributors_email	string	Email of any individuals or institutions that contributed to the collection of this data (separated by comma)		
NC_GLOBAL	contributors_name	string	Name of any individuals or institutions that contributed to the collection of this data (separated by comma)		
NC_GLOBAL	contributors_orcid	string	ORCID of any individuals or institutions that contributed to the collection of this data (separated by comma)		ORCID
NC_GLOBAL	contributors_role	string	Role of any individuals or institutions that contributed to the collection of this data (separated by comma)		
NC_GLOBAL	creator_email	string	Email of data creator	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	creator_name	string	Name of data creator	yes	

NC_GLOBAL	creator_type	string	Type of data creator (e.g., person, institution)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	creator_url	string	URL of data creator	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	defaultGraphQuery	string			
NC_GLOBAL	Easternmost_Easting				
NC_GLOBAL	featureType	String			
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lat_max	double	Max latitude expressed in WGS84 (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	WGS84
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lat_min	double	Min latitude expressed in WGS84 (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	WGS84
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lat_units	string	Degrees north	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lon_max	double	Max longitude expressed in WGS84 (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	WGS84
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lon_min	double	Min longitude expressed in WGS84 (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data	WGS84
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lon_units	string	Degrees east	yes, if spatial data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lat_resolution	double	Latitude resolution expressed in WGS84 (for grid data)	yes, if spatial grid data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_lon_resolution	double	Longitude resolution expressed in WGS84 (for grid data)	yes, if spatial grid data	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_vertical_max	double	Max vertical extension (in case of vertical profile) (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data and exists depth	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_vertical_min	double	Min vertical extension (in case of vertical profile) (the highest possible precision)	yes, if spatial data and exists depth	

NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_vertical_positive	string	Positive direction of vertical extension ("up" means that z increases up - height, "down" means that z increases downward - pressure or depth)	yes, if spatial data and exists depth	
NC_GLOBAL	geospatial_vertical_units	string	Units used for the vertical extension	yes, if spatial data and exists depth	
NC_GLOBAL	infoUrl	string	URL of data information background (es. project web page, dataset page, ...)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	inspire	string	INSPIRE spatial data or SeaDataNet vocabulary	yes, if spatial data	INSPIRE Spatial Data Themes (GEMET)
NC_GLOBAL	institution	string	Institution principally responsible for this data (owner or provider)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	institution_edmo_code	string	EDMO code of the institution principally responsible for this data (owner or provider)	yes	EDMO SeaDataNet
NC_GLOBAL	institution_country	string	Country of the institution principally responsible for this data (owner or provider) expressed according to ISO 3166	yes	ISO 3166
NC_GLOBAL	keywords	string	List of keywords and phrases (separated by comma - in case of multiple vocabularies, insert keywords following the same order listed in "keywords_vocabulary")	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	keywords_vocabulary	string	Identifies the controlled list of keywords from which the values in the "keywords" attribute are taken (in case of multiple vocabularies, separated by comma)	yes	e.g.: Global Change Master Directory (GCMD)
NC_GLOBAL	licence	string	Licence that describes the restrictions to data access and distribution	yes	Creative commons
NC_GLOBAL	naming_authority	string	Name of who defines the data set and the standards to be applied	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	Northernmost_Northing	double			
NC_GLOBAL	Principal_Tidal_Constituents	string			

NC_GLOBAL	references	string	Description of how the dataset was created: published or web-based references that describe the data or methods used to produce it. Recommend URIs (such as a URL or DOI) for papers or other references. This attribute is defined in the CF conventions	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	source	string	The method of collection and production of the dataset (e.g., types of instrument, model, collection). If it was model-generated, source should name the model and its version. If it is observational, source should characterize it. This attribute is defined in the CF Conventions	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	sourceUrl		per ERDDAP		
NC_GLOBAL	Southernmost_Northing	double			
NC_GLOBAL	standard_name_vocabulary	string	Name and version of standard vocabulary (e.g., CF Standard Name Table v70)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	subsetVariables	string	per ERDDAP		
NC_GLOBAL	summary	string	A paragraph describing the dataset, analogous to an abstract for a paper	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	testOutOfDate	string	per ERDDAP		
NC_GLOBAL	time_coverage_duration	string	Time coverage duration using ISO 8601 (in alternative to time_coverage_start/time_coverage_end)	yes, if available	ISO 8601
NC_GLOBAL	time_coverage_end	string	Time coverage end using ISO 8601	yes	ISO 8601
NC_GLOBAL	time_coverage_start	string	Time coverage start using ISO 8601	yes	ISO 8601
NC_GLOBAL	time_coverage_resolution	string	Time coverage resolution using ISO 8601 (if applicable)	yes, if applicable	ISO 8601
NC_GLOBAL	title	string	Dataset title (a short phrase or sentence describing the dataset)	yes	
NC_GLOBAL	variables	string	List of variables id (separated by comma)	yes	

NC_GLOBAL	Westernmost_Easting	double			
data	data_centre				
data	data_centre_email				
data	data_creation	string	Date of dataset creation	yes	ISO 8601
data	data_doi	string	Data DOI	yes, if existing	
data	data_update	string	Date of dataset update	yes	ISO 8601
data	data_version	string	Dataset update version or user manual version	yes	
platform	platform_type	string	Type of platform		NERC Vocabulary L06
platform	platform_id_orig	string	Pre-existing platform id, if applicable		
platform	platform_id	string	Platform id of defined for the Project		
project	oceanographic_campaign	string	Name of the oceanographic campaign during which the data of the specific project were collected		
ship	ship_name	string	Name of the ship (e.g., "Belgica")		
ship	ship_imo	double	IMO ship identification number (unique ship identifier) - report only the seven-digit number (e.g. "9871294")		Marine Traffic Research
ship	ship_call_sign	string	Maritime call sign assigned as unique alphanumeric identifier to the ship (e.g., "ORCO")		
sensor	sensor_model	string	Sensor URL		NERC Vocabulary L22
variable	standard_name	string	Standard name of the variable	yes	NERC Vocabulary P09, P02, P01, P07, P33
variable	_CoordinateAxisType	String			-
variable	_FillValue	float			-
variable	actual_range	double			-
variable	axis	String			-
variable	cf_role				-
variable	colorBarMaximum	double			-
variable	colorBarMinimum	double			-
variable	conventions				-

variable	ioos_category	String			-
variable	long_name	string	Long name of the variable	yes	
variable	owner	long_name			
variable	PlatformCode	long_name			
variable	qc_indicator	string	Quality Control Flag Level	yes, if applicable	OceanSITES Data Format Reference Manual (for ocean data)
variable	qc_manual	string	Quality Control Flag Scheme	yes, if applicable	OceanSITES Data Format Reference Manual (for ocean data)
variable	qc_method	string	Quality Control Flag Method (DOI or other reference)	yes, if applicable	
variable	sensor_model	string	Sensor URL	yes, if applicable	NERC Vocabulary L22
variable	source_name				-
variable	standard_name	String			-
variable	time_origin	String			-
variable	time_precision	String			-
variable	units	String		yes, if applicable	

Variable name	Description	Data type	Description	Mandatory	Vocabulary
project	project_name	string	Project name	yes	CORDIS for European Project
project	project_code	string	Project code/acronym	yes	CORDIS for European Project
project	project_id	double	Project Grant agreement number	yes	CORDIS for European Project
project	project_statement	string	Project Grant agreement statement	yes	CORDIS for European Project
project	Project_DOI	string	Project DOI	yes	CORDIS for European Project
project	project_edmerp	string	Project EDMERP code	yes	EDMERP SeaDataNet
project	Link				